

Model-Driven Right-Sizing of Offloading in Data Processing Pipelines

Faeze Faghieh
Technical University of Darmstadt
Darmstadt, Germany
faeze.faghieh@tu-darmstadt.de

Florin Dinu*
Nokia Bell Labs
Stuttgart, Germany
florin.dinu@nokia-bell-labs.com

Maximilian Hüttner
Technical University of Darmstadt
Darmstadt, Germany
maximilian.huettner@tu-darmstadt.de

Zsolt István
Technical University of Darmstadt
Darmstadt, Germany
zsolt.istvan@tu-darmstadt.de

Abstract

The performance of modern Big Data systems used for data processing is often bottlenecked by data movement across various components. Offloading part of the processing closer to the storage and network to reduce this bottleneck is a compelling idea, and in today's hardware landscape, there are many different types of Smart Storage, Smart NIC, or Smart Switch devices one could choose from. One challenge, however, is that it is often unclear at design time what improvements of the end workload one can achieve with a given hardware. Co-design is typically mentioned in related work as the solution, but it is far from obvious what this entails in practice: what information about the hardware, software system, and workload is taken into account for decision-making is often implicit in related work.

In this work, we propose a model-driven methodology for right-sizing offloading to benefit an end workload. Our methodology determines the target processing rate an offload device should have in a specific data processing system, without over-fitting. This helps designers pick the right hardware for offloading. Our methodology relies on modeling the system as a network of queues, based on different levels of information about the system, which allows determining the general usefulness of offload and the specific benefits to a workload of interest. We demonstrate how our methodology avoids under- or over-provisioning offload devices in a case study.

CCS Concepts

• **Information systems** → **Data management systems**; • **Theory of computation** → **Models of computation**; • **Computer systems organization** → **Distributed architectures**.

Keywords

Data Processing Pipelines, Right-Sized Offloading Methodology, Heterogeneous Hardware

*Work carried out while at Huawei Munich Research Center, Germany.

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. *DaMoN '25, Berlin, Germany*

© 2025 Copyright held by the owner/author(s).
ACM ISBN 979-8-4007-1940-0/25/06
<https://doi.org/10.1145/3736227.3736239>

ACM Reference Format:

Faeze Faghieh, Maximilian Hüttner, Florin Dinu, and Zsolt István. 2025. Model-Driven Right-Sizing of Offloading in Data Processing Pipelines. In *21st International Workshop on Data Management on New Hardware (DaMoN '25)*, June 22–27, 2025, Berlin, Germany. ACM, New York, NY, USA, 8 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3736227.3736239>

1 Introduction

Data-intensive applications in the cloud and datacenter often face performance bottlenecks due to data movement. Near-data processing (NDP), in the storage device [10], network interface card [6], or in the network switches [13], is often proposed as a solution. In addition to the physical location of the NDP device, there is also a wide range of hardware options for processing: ranging from Application Specific Integrated Circuits (ASICs) [9, 10] through Field Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs) [16, 24] to low power CPUs [2, 6]. With NDP devices commonly available in data centers and clouds, one barrier to adoption has been lowered, but it is still challenging to determine if and which specific NDP device can be useful in a workload.

As an additional challenge, the developers who are experts in programming NDP devices are typically not experts in the inner workings of the Big Data system at hand, yet they need to consider properties of the system and workload on the following aspects: (1) *Preventing under- or over-provisioning*: When deciding how much of the NDP device resources to set aside for processing the offload, it is crucial that the NDP device does not accidentally become a performance bottleneck. At the same time, over-provisioning (e.g., to obtain the highest possible offload processing rate) can lead to wasted resources and increased energy consumption (e.g., the highest rate may not be sustainable in a workload due to downstream bottlenecks). While determining the useful performance range of an NDP device is a clear requirement, in some related works that only focus on the hardware design, aspects of how the NDP offload is connected to data sources and software systems are not taken into account. Our methodology begins with establishing the useful performance range of NDP when deployed in a specific system, regardless of the exact workload.

(2) *The need for a workload-wide view of data selectivity*: In addition to the general system architecture and link speeds, the workload-dependent data selectivity of operators is also important to consider. Low selectivity of an operator reduces the bandwidth

usage to the next operator, allowing for potentially faster offloading. As a result, even if the NDP device has been provisioned to meet the next link bandwidth target, it will effectively be under-provisioned in cases of low selectivity. Such effects can be compounded with the selectivity of operators. Hence, we need to look beyond single operators and consider the overall workload to right-size offloading. Our methodology does exactly this by instrumenting the operators of a data system and capturing workload-level statistics.

Our goal is to remove the guessing and uncertainty from determining the right offloading for a workload, making it easier for NDP developers to design and build right-sized offloading devices while requiring metrics with minimal modifications to the software code base. By right-sizing, we refer to the process of determining the target processing rate of the offload for a specific operator. Given an NDP device and a workload, our paper proposes a methodology for doing right-sizing. We also discuss the implications of tailoring the NDP implementation to the determined target rate.

Our methodology builds on a unified way of modeling systems, offload devices with their processing unit, and workloads, and gathering information at three levels (which doesn't need to be done in order) for the model: A) nominal performance numbers and specifications of hardware components, B) micro-benchmarks of the operators in the specific software system, and C) workload-specific metrics, capturing the exact behavior of the computations of interest. Our methodology helps the NDP designer to not only learn about a good "point solution" but to gather a holistic view of the design space. They will be able to find an answer to, in general, what range of offloading rates could be promising for any system running on the given hardware, more specifically, what rates are promising for the system at hand, and most specifically, what is the target rate to provide for a workload of interest? With this information, and depending on the development cost of the offload logic (e.g., is it an FPGA-based solution designed from scratch, or is the NDP designer writing software for an existing platform), a well-founded decision can be taken on what processing rate to aim.

To demonstrate that our methodology is not just an academic exercise and is useful in practice, we provide a case study exploring the usefulness of near-data processing in a modern streaming analytics system, NebulaStream [27]. We also use this example to explain how systems should be instrumented to measure the operator and workload-level metrics necessary for the model. We furthermore validate the output from our model with an FPGA-based offloading prototype we implemented.

2 The Proposed Methodology

2.1 Assumptions and Non-Goals

We assume that the NDP developer has already chosen a data processing system and a specific workload, as well as one (or several) operators to potentially offload; and they want to determine the performance range that the offloading module needs to fall into in order to benefit the overall system. This determination made using our methodology can serve as the basis for multiple higher-level decisions: designing new application-specific hardware module (e.g., using an FPGA clean-slate design), choosing between different commercial SmartSSDs, deciding whether a specific NDP device is useful or not in a specific workload, and many more.

Figure 1: We adapt NoQ models to be used in our methodology

We abstract away most execution details and consider data processing pipelines that pass batches of data (tuples) between operators on physical machines. Serialization techniques, data formats, etc., become implicit in our approach, and their performance impact is captured in the behavior of the operators. Even though this is a very general abstraction, it fits streaming systems well, as it also fits vectorized database engines. In general, we are interested in the processing rate (i.e., Bytes per second) of all data transmission links and operators, as well as their selectivity (in case they reduce or inflate data). We assume that the measured processing rate of an operator is not influenced by its selectivity.

When modeling, often one of the goals is to predict the behavior of the system (e.g., response time, throughput, energy consumption) for unseen workloads. This is a non-goal for this work. Our methodology focuses on determining the properties of an offload module that would be beneficial for the workload at hand. Furthermore, it is also not our goal to identify secondary bottlenecks in the software implementation, as this would require more in-depth analysis of system internals and intrusive statistics gathering.

2.2 Network of Queues as a Unified Model

The processing elements in NDP devices can vary, including ARM processors, FPGAs, and ASICs, while server processors also differ. To address this heterogeneity, we require a model that abstracts away the internal details of processing steps. We chose Network-of-Queues (NoQ) [18], a well-established technique that enables us to represent systems consisting of multiple "devices", each with its own queue and a specific service rate (this service rate can be load-dependent to represent parallelism). Figure 1a shows a representation of a system in NoQ. The jobs enter the system and visit each device to get service, after which they leave the system. NoQ relies on the assumption that all jobs entering the system are equal (there is no prioritization, and all are processed uniformly).

The inputs to the NoQ are:

- (1) **The External Job Arrival Rate** of the incoming jobs to the system, shown as X in Figure 1a. In our representation, jobs map to batches of records, e.g., the size of a disk page.
- (2) **Visit Ratio of each device:** The fraction of the jobs visiting device i from the number of incoming jobs to the system.

Table 1: Structure of our methodology, with what inputs and outputs are provided

Focus on:	Inputs to the Model	Topology	Missing Inputs	Outputs
A: General Hardware Components	Component Specifications: Storage Bandwidth, Link Bandwidth	Single topology	1) Selectivity: assumed to be in [1%-100%] 2) Performance of software system: assumed to be larger than link	The range of meaningful offloading rates (for the upper and lower bound of selectivity)
B: Specific System	Information from A and Micro-Benchmarks of System: Upstream and downstream operators of interest, Stand-alone measurements of operators	Multiple: One for each "upstream-offload-downstream" combination	1) Selectivity: assumed to be in [1%-100%]	1) A range of meaningful offloading rates for each topology 2) If these ranges are overlapping: there is a chance that offloading could be beneficial for all combinations
C: Specific Workload	Information from A and B, plus Workload Measurements: List and performance of operators in each query, Selectivity of each operator in each query	Multiple: One for each query in workload	–	1) The ideal rate for each query 2) If these rates are close: the offloading would benefit all queries without being severely over-provisioned for any of them

In our approach, this property can be used to capture the implications of the selectivity of a preceding operator.

- (3) **The Service Rate of each device:** The number of jobs per unit of time that this device can process. To represent parallelism, the service rate can be a function of the number of jobs in the system, increasing linearly until the parallelism limit is reached.

Among the outputs of the NoQ model, the utilization per device is of particular interest to us. It quantifies the fraction of time each device is actively processing, and the device with the highest utilization is considered the bottleneck device.

Note that in a pure NoQ representation, the device connection topology is not required to compute outputs, as the underlying assumptions dictate that the processing time for each job is independent of the order in which devices are visited. In this work, we compute the *visit ratio* of each device depending on the operators' order (topology) in a workload, considering selectivity and potential data transformation. In a simplified way, a device's visit ratio is the product of its upstream neighbor's visit ratio and its selectivity. Figure 1b illustrates this calculation for four devices (four query operators). Visit ratios are also adjusted in the topology in case processing is split into coarse-grained parallel pipelines.

In our model, both operators and communication links are modeled as devices; each is assigned a *service rate*. For operators, this can be determined in micro-benchmarks or full queries by measuring the time spent processing (excluding idle time due to input delays or downstream buffer constraints) and the amount of data processed. For network links, nominal bandwidths can be used.

When building a model only based on micro-benchmarks, without considering the real-world data characteristics, operator selectivity remains unknown. In our modeling methodology, we create a "lower bound" and an "upper bound" model to study the behavior assuming a selectivity ranging from 1% to 100% (while certain applications may result in selectivity exceeding 100%, e.g., decompression, we omit these cases for simplicity).

In our methodology, we use Mean Value Analysis (MVA) [20] to identify the bottleneck device (i.e., which is the device with the highest utilization). The high-level approach is shown in Algorithm 1; note that the "operator" notion in the algorithm may represent multiple operators (e.g., filter and scan operators can be treated as a single operator). **Our goal is to identify the lowest**

Algorithm 1 Using MVA to determine the processing rate of a specific operator.

Inputs:

- For each operator O_i : processing_rate: P_i and selectivity: Sel_i
- Topology (as a DAG) + operator of interest O_p

Outputs:

- Processing rate for O_p

Algorithm:

- 1: Calculate each visit ratio V_i based on topology and preceding operator selectivities
- 2: **For** each operator O_i
Calculate: $processing_rate(P_i) / visit_ratio(V_i)$
- 3: Exclude the operator of interest O_p from the topology
- 4: Based on the Utilization Law in MVA find the operator in the topology with the lowest value of $P_i/V_i = VP$ (i.e., the bottleneck operator)
- 5: Output processing rate: $VP \times V_{O_p}$

processing rate for offloading such that offloading is not the bottleneck – any rate higher than this will not increase the pipeline throughput (i.e., leading to over-provisioning), albeit it might reduce response times. Our general model, however, will not be able to predict latency improvements accurately.

2.3 Obtaining the Inputs to the Model

We collect data for the model and generate outputs across three levels of abstraction (also shown in Table 1), starting with useful NDP rates in a specific hardware architecture, then refining them for a specific data processing system, and finally, in the context of a specific set of queries. The information necessary to build the model is obtained as follows at each level:

Level A: Gathering Component Specifications. We rely on hardware vendor specifications for this level, such as the storage read bandwidth and link bandwidths. As shown in Table 1, in this case, we do not yet have information on specific operators, their composition, or their selectivities. Therefore, the model consists of a data source, the offloading module, and the rest of the system. We build the model with a selectivity range for the offloaded operator (e.g., 1% to 100%) and derive both lower and upper bounds for the target processing rate instead of a single value.

In terms of service rate, in this level of abstraction, we assume that the operations after the offloading can be carried out at the same rate as the data source, so that they are not the bottleneck. This, naturally, could lead to an overestimation of how fast the offloading needs to be, it is a safe assumption given the lack of detailed information at this stage.

Figure 2: The model representation based on increasingly refined information: from approximate to precise.

Level B: Micro-benchmarking of Operators. In order to capture the general behavior of a data processing system, micro-benchmarking can be carried out. In addition to the information from Level A, this level provides a list of available software operators and their processing rates. Since we do not know the exact topology, a “family” of models has to be built, considering triplets of operations: an operation that could feed the offload, followed by the offload operator, followed by an operation that could consume its output. The selectivity is still unknown at this level, which means that the model output will be a range of processing rates. Using the information about the system, we can determine (i) what is the useful range common across all combinations (the overlap of all ranges) and (ii) what is the highest meaningful processing rate for the offload module that would still benefit at least one operator combination.

Level C: Workload-specific Measurements. In this level, workload-specific measurements and the topology of queries with selectivities yield a very precise model, but it also becomes “overfitted” by definition. To collect information for C, we instrument the system to gather the statistics and run the target workload (in §3, we explain in detail how to do this in a streaming analytics system). To measure the operator rates, it is crucial to instrument the code such that only busy time (i.e., the time spent purely on processing) is measured without queuing time. For a given workload, each query can be modeled individually, and for each model, the useful offloading rate can be determined precisely.

3 Case Study on Operator Offloading to Computational Storage

Our case study uses Multes [15, 16], a 100Gbps key-value store built with FPGAs, as the data source in NebulaStream [27], a streaming data analytics system specifically designed for edge/cloud environments and for heterogeneous hardware nodes. We also use Flink [7], which is a widely used streaming and batch processing system.

For NebulaStream and Flink, we use 3 nodes (1 coordinator and 2 workers) connected by a 100 Gbps interconnect and featuring a 3 GHz 32-core AMD EPYC CPU. For Multes, we used a network-attached AMD Alveo U55C FPGA [1]. As the workload, we run the Star Schema Benchmark (SSB)[19] SF=1 in NebulaStream and Flink.

Since Multes supports user-defined processing on key-value pairs read from its storage, we focused on the filtering operator and asked, *if we offloaded the filter operator to the FPGA, at what rate should the FPGA filter data?* This helps pick the right design in hardware and save resources.

3.1 Applying the Methodology in NebulaStream

Level A. Relying just on specifications. As described in §2.3, the first level is to use nominal specifications for determining a first approximation of the processing rate. Figure 2a illustrates the built NoQ representation for this scenario. As only the storage and link bandwidths are available, our NoQ representation has four devices: storage, offload filter, link, and NebulaStream. NebulaStream is assumed not to be a bottleneck.

The read bandwidth from storage in Multes is at most 14.9 GB/s, and the link bandwidth between Multes and the server node running the NebulaStream worker has been measured at 4.5 GB/s with iPerf. Since the selectivity of the filter operator is unknown at this level, we consider a range of selectivities in [1% - 100%]. The resulting range for the offload processing rate is shown in Table 2 at [4.5 GB/ - 14.9 GB/s] (note that the lower rate actually corresponds to the 100% selectivity case). This range will be gradually refined in the subsequent levels.

Level B. Benchmarking the system operators. By analyzing NebulaStream, we can identify a list of operators and benchmark their processing rates. As a result, we can create a list of potential downstream operators in the topology. In our case, there are no upstream operators, as the offload reads directly from storage. Our methodology, nonetheless, can also handle the scenarios with multiple upstream operators (e.g., when additional operators exist between storage and offload). The potential selectivity of the operators is still unknown at this level. Therefore, we work with an expected selectivity range [1% - 100%] and calculate the offload rate with different combinations of downstream operators.

To measure the processing rate of operators, we made minimal changes to NebulaStream. Our model requires busy time measurements of operators, which we obtain by adding timestamps before and after the execution of each batch of tuples. We also track the number of processed tuples per operator, and finally calculate the processing rate as the ratio of processed data size to busy time. In practice, as shown in Figure 3, operator processing rates vary across experiments– this can be because their implementation exhibits variations between repetitions or workload factors such as tuple size. As a result, selecting a single representative rate– or a range–

Table 2: Our methodology applied to NebulaStream and Flink, targeting filtering offload to an FPGA-based data source.

Information Level	Offload range(s) in NebulaStream	Offload range(s) in Flink	Comments
A: Component Specifications	[4.5 GB/s - 14.9 GB/s]	[4.5 GB/s - 14.9 GB/s]	Offloading is bound by the data source and the link bandwidths. Processing at >14.9 GB/s might reduce latency, but does not increase the pipeline throughput.
B: Micro-Benchmarks of Scan, Filter, Join	Scan+Parse: [0.2 MB/s - 120 MB/s] Filter: [0.058 GB/s - 14.9 GB/s] Join: [<1 MB/s - 14.9 GB/s]	Scan+Parse: [884 MB/s - 14.9 GB/s] Filter: [131 MB/s - 13.09 GB/s] Join: [90 MB/s - 9.03 GB/s]	Due to integration details, the offload logic will have to be followed by a Parse operator in software
C: Workload Measurements of SSB	Q1.x: (4.28, 12) MB/s Q2.x, Q3.x and Q4.x: <1 MB/s	Q1.x: (777, 2041) MB/s Q2.x: 156 MB/s Q3.x: (156,1091) MB/s Q4.x: (156,1091,4364) MB/s	In queries 2, 3, and 4, the offloading can be applied only to very small tables. The bottleneck is in scanning another table, hence the offloading rate almost does not matter in NebulaStream.

Figure 3: Operator rates in NebulaStream. For our NoQ model, lower and upper performance bounds suffice; there is no need for detailed mappings. For each operator, we can obtain looser **micro-benchmark** bounds (Min_B/Max_B for Level B) and tighter **workload-specific** bounds (Min_W/Max_W for Level C). Red points show workload-specific numbers. In (c), each color shows the rate for a specific right tuple size.

requires careful consideration. Note that if the goal were to predict the system behavior for future queries, a more complex function would be needed to approximate operator behavior. In our case, however, we can pick, for instance, the highest observed rate of an operator (see green lines in Figure 3), to define the threshold for under-provisioning for offloading. With this choice, it is guaranteed that no operator will be slowed down when using the offloading. In case the system can rely on a query scheduler to decide at run-time whether to use hardware offloading or not, then rates closer to the minimum or averages of bounds in Figure 3 can also be chosen. At such a rate, offload would still be beneficial for at least some operators, with the scheduler making sure that slowdowns are avoided.

Via micro-benchmarking, we measured the filter rate for different tuple sizes and obtained the range [58.2 MB/s - 165 MB/s] (Figure 3a green). After accounting for the operator selectivity ranging between [1% - 100%], the range becomes [58.2 MB/s - 14.9 GB/s] as in the second column of Table 2. We benchmark scan+parse as a function of the tuple size (the table size is not relevant because this operator reads and parses one buffer-sized chunk of data at a time) and obtain [0.2 MB/s - 1.2 MB/s] (Figure 3b green) and [0.2 MB/s - 120 MB/s] (Table 2) after accounting for the selectivity range. For joins, we focus on the faster hash join variant. This operator is blocking, and its rate depends on the number of rows in the left and right tables. Figure 3c shows the behavior of a join when the size

of input tables varies: the right table size is depicted using colors, and the left table size is depicted on the x-axis. The processing rate in Figure 3c is shown as tuples/sec to give a better insight into the actual join rate, but for inclusion in the NoQ representation, we transform it into the range [0.12 MB/s - 4.24 GB/s]. An interesting observation in Table 2 is the shift in the useful offload rate range between Level A and Level B when incorporating micro-benchmark results alongside nominal specifications. This is caused by the fact that the operators have a lower processing rate in comparison to the nominal specification (also, we need to assume a wide range of selectivities, expanding the rate options).

Level C. Workload-Specific Measurements. In this level, we consider the SSB queries as the workload. The red lines in Figures 3c and 3b show the possible range of the join and scan+parse operators in this workload. By including these numbers in the analysis, it is possible to calculate the target offload rate for the SSB queries. The very small rates (e.g., 0.000259 MB/s, presented as <1MB/s in Table 2) occur when the query bottleneck is a different operator. For example, in Query 1.2 (topology shown in Figure 2c), which includes two tables as the data source (lineorder table and date table are stored on two separate nodes, as indicated by two storage devices in the figure), in case of having the lineorder filter as the offload candidate, the target rate is 12 MB/s. Conversely, having the date filter as the candidate,

Figure 4: On the FPGA, selecting an appropriate hardware design can result in substantial resource savings. In our case study, a simple Iterative design is sufficient to meet the target rate, making a parallel parser/filter design unnecessary for NebulaStream.

the target rate is 0.000259 MB/s. The reason for this low rate is that the bottleneck is the scan of the lineorder table, which is 2000x larger than the date table. As a result, a low rate from the date filter is sufficient. Comparing this rate with the output of the previous levels, the target offload rate is more precise, which reveals that NDP devices with smaller processing rates could also be suitable candidates for offloading.

3.2 Applying the Methodology in Flink

In this section, we briefly discuss the results of applying our methodology to Flink to showcase that it broadly applies to systems with different internal architectures. Flink is a well-known stream and batch processing system; executing both paradigms within a pipelined dataflow engine [7]. Unlike NebulaStream, Flink provides a monitoring tool to get, among other statistics, each operator’s busy time, idle time, and backpressured time, without requiring modification to the source code.

As shown in Table 2, our methodology determines a higher processing rate for filter offloading in Flink compared to NebulaStream. Flink supports fine-grained resource allocation, allowing a specific amount of memory and CPU cores to be assigned to each operator. In future work, we plan to investigate improving resource utilization by applying our methodology to determine the resource requirements for individual Flink operators.

3.3 Picking the Right FPGA Design for Filtering

3.3.1 Design Alternatives. There are two major design options for implementing filter operators on FPGAs. As a first option, filtering can be expressed as a state machine, with conditions being evaluated iteratively (see the left-hand side of Figure 4). Such an iterative design has the advantage that it requires only narrow data lines and,

given that most basic data types in analytics workloads are aligned to 4-byte words, this means that few resources have to be spent on the reconstruction of values or tuples. The main drawback of such an iterative design is that, even if clocked high, its throughput remains modest, in the order of GB/s (assuming a clock rate between 200-400 MHz).

As a second design option, filtering can also be provided as a data-parallel processing unit where wide vectors of column values are processed in a pipelined manner. Such a design has the advantage of higher throughput than the iterative one (see the right-hand side of Figure 4), but this comes at the cost of significantly increased resource consumption. The resource cost is not only coming from the increase in the number of parallel comparators for the wide vectors. If this were the case, the resource difference should be a similar multiplier as for throughput. Instead, the additional logic required for realigning incoming data to the wide vector units (shown as “Realignment Logic” in the figure) can take up a significant part of the chip. Since incoming tuples may vary in width, the realignment stage has to align tuples within registers before further processing, such as parsing and filtering (the crossbar-like logic shown in the figure). If a wide register is realigned at a per-bit granularity, it results in a significant increase in resource usage. Furthermore, the parsing logic must examine all positions in the register in parallel, which is another contributor to the high resource consumption. In conclusion, depending on the basic data types and possible misalignment, such a parallel design can have a quadratic resource consumption increase for wider data paths.

3.3.2 Choice for NebulaStream. When designing a filter kernel for our NDP use-case and considering only the nominal storage bandwidths of NebulaStream and Flink, the kernel must achieve a processing rate of 14.9 GB/s. To meet this processing rate at a

clock frequency of approximately 250 MHz (which is typical for FPGAs), the kernel requires a 512-bit input width – requiring a parallel design for the kernel.

As it is shown in Table 2, however, the processing rate of such a parallel design will be significantly higher than NebulaStream’s operators, and somewhat higher than Flink’s, indicating that the allocated resources would not be fully utilized. Therefore, if the NDP design is intended solely for NebulaStream, a more resource-efficient Iterative alternative should be considered. It is beneficial to prioritize lower resource consumption at the cost of reduced throughput. Based on the required processing rate for NebulaStream in Table 2, a kernel running at 250 MHz would only need a 32-bit input width to meet the bandwidth demand. As shown in Figure 4b, this version processes 32 bits per cycle and requires substantially fewer FPGA resources. It might be even possible to run it at a higher frequency, thus reaching a throughput of 1.5 GB/s (which is more than enough for NebulaStream).

We integrated the two FPGA filter kernel variants into Multes and used them as the “smart storage” for NebulaStream. The system behaved as predicted by the model. For instance, for Query 1.1, the processing rate increases from 0.6 MB/s to almost 4.1 MB/s (which is the target rate in Table 2). This speedup occurs because, by offloading the filter operator to storage, the visit ratio of the scan in Node 1 of Figure 2c decreases. Making the FPGA filter faster will not significantly reduce query latency due to the blocking nature of the join operators in NebulaStream.

3.4 Leveraging our methodology to re-evaluate an alternative platform.

As part of our initial exploration of possible platforms, we evaluated the NGD Newport Smart NVMe drive [2] as a potential Smart Data Source for NebulaStream. This device features an additional ARM processor, which offers flexible offloading capabilities. The ARM processor is inserted inside the device and is connected to the flash storage through a PCIe switch, enabling direct data access. However, performance limitations led to its dismissal, including slower ARM CPU read speeds (~700 MB/s, while the host can perform random access read at 1.2GB/s) and a bottlenecked host-to-CPU connection (70 MB/s). With the insights from our methodology, the initial negative decision could be revisited, as the drive may still meet the target rates outlined in Table 2, potentially offering a more efficient solution.

4 Related Work

In our case study, we explored the benefits of using an FPGA-based Smart Storage in a data processing pipeline. There have been many different platforms proposed in recent years for similar purposes [8, 10, 17, 24, 25], but they typically represent “point solutions” in a very large design space in terms of processing hardware type and nominal processing rate [5]. With our methodology, we make it easy to answer what offloading rates are useful for an application, which, in turn, will help in picking the right platform for offloading.

To perform the right-sizing, we do not need to precisely model the response time of the system, nor do we have to make higher-level optimizations related to resource allocation – by keeping these tasks out of scope, we are able to provide a generalizable

approach that does not “overfit”. Nonetheless, once a range for useful offloading rates has been determined, it could be beneficial to investigate response times of different hardware design options. There is interesting related work that creates fine-grained models fit for describing very specific hardware/software combinations. Some, like LogNIC [11] aims to model SmartNIC platforms. LogNIC employs a packet-centric approach and targets the heterogeneous computation domain adopted by SmartNICs and the building blocks in a SmartNIC program (e.g., packet header manipulation). Unlike LogNIC, which exclusively targets SmartNIC applications, our approach addresses a broader class of heterogeneous systems.

LogCA [3] offers a simple, high-level model for domain-specific accelerators that are deployed “on the side” of a host system, not in the data path. The purpose of LogCA is similar to our work, namely, assisting early-stage architectural decisions. However, LogCA focuses on a host-centric compute paradigm where data is transferred from the host to the accelerator, and results are copied back.

Similarly to LogCA, Accelerometer [22] focuses on accelerators with a very specific deployment model in mind, namely, deployed in microservices in the cloud. The primary objective of Accelerometer is similar to ours: to identify offload-induced overheads early in the hardware design process. The methods proposed in Accelerometer, however, do not apply to pipelined processing scenarios, which is a key distinction of our approach.

There are also works that set out to make better resource allocation decisions at runtime based on, e.g., Machine Learning-based cost models [12, 14, 23], but they typically abstract away many processing details that are relevant in the context of our work. For instance, the fact that processing pipelines can be represented as dataflow graphs that make it easy to reason about bottleneck devices under different theoretical setups is often simplified away in ML-based approaches.

Our methodology does help with determining whether a specific functionality should be offloaded or not, and at what target rate the offloading should work. Programming and managing the NDP devices is external to our work, but nonetheless, very important. There are an increasing number of high-level programming models and runtime services for offloading [4, 21, 26]. These allow NDP programmers to reuse code across platforms and benefit from newer generations of hardware. An interesting venue for future work is the combination of our methodology with a runtime service, to take offload decisions based on the observed and modeled behavior of the system.

5 Conclusion

This paper presents a methodology for right-sizing offloading in data processing pipelines. This is important as it allows us to utilize heterogeneous hardware resources efficiently and make software systems faster or more efficient overall. Our methodology is designed to be adaptable across different levels of available information to the NDP programmers, without requiring deep system expertise, and enables them to make an informed decision on what offloading processing rates to target at design time.

We evaluated our methodology using a real-world case study with the NebulaStream data analytics system and the Multes key-value store. By applying it to this case, we could show that the

range of useful offloading rates could be significantly narrowed down, resulting in a better choice of design for the FPGA offloading. Our methodology enables us to reduce resource consumption by almost 32x for an FPGA without negatively impacting performance. In our future work, we aim to leverage our methodology alongside Flink's fine-grained resource allocation feature to determine the resource requirements of individual operators (i.e., CPU and Memory), integrate these insights into the allocator, and explore if this can enhance resource utilization.

Acknowledgments

This work was funded partially through a research grant from Huawei Munich Research Center, Germany, and partially by the European Union through the CHORYS HORIZON-RIA project. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

References

- [1] 2024. AMD Alveo Product Sheet. <https://www.amd.com/en/products/accelerators/alveo/u55c/a-u55c-p00g-pq-g.html>.
- [2] 2024. NGD Systems Computation Storage Wesbite. <https://www.ngdsystems.com/technology/computational-storage/>.
- [3] Muhammad Shoaib Bin Altaf and David A Wood. 2017. Logca: A high-level performance model for hardware accelerators. *ACM SIGARCH Computer Architecture News* 45, 2 (2017), 375–388.
- [4] Antonio Barbalace, Martin Decky, Javier Picorel, and Pramod Bhatotia. 2020. BlockNDP: Block-storage near data processing. In *Proceedings of the 21st International Middleware Conference Industrial Track*. 8–15.
- [5] Antonio Barbalace and Jaeyoung Do. 2021. Computational storage: Where are we today?. In *Conference on Innovative Data Systems Research 2020*.
- [6] Idan Burstein. 2021. Nvidia data center processing unit (dpu) architecture. In *2021 IEEE Hot Chips 33 Symposium (HCS)*. IEEE, 1–20.
- [7] Paris Carbone, Asterios Katsifodimos, Stephan Ewen, Volker Markl, Seif Haridi, and Kostas Tzoumas. 2015. Apache flink: Stream and batch processing in a single engine. *The Bulletin of the Technical Committee on Data Engineering* 38, 4 (2015).
- [8] Jaeyoung Do, Yang-Suk Kee, Jignesh M Patel, Chanik Park, Kwanghyun Park, and David J DeWitt. 2013. Query processing on smart ssds: Opportunities and challenges. In *Proceedings of the 2013 ACM SIGMOD International Conference on Management of Data*. 1221–1230.
- [9] Yuanwei Fang, Chen Zou, Aaron J Elmore, and Andrew A Chien. 2017. UDP: a programmable accelerator for extract-transform-load workloads and more. In *Proceedings of the 50th Annual IEEE/ACM International Symposium on Microarchitecture*. 55–68.
- [10] Boncheol Gu, Andre S Yoon, Duck-Ho Bae, Insoon Jo, Jinyoung Lee, Jonghyun Yoon, Jeong-Uk Kang, Moonsang Kwon, Chanho Yoon, Sangyeun Cho, et al. 2016. Biscuit: A framework for near-data processing of big data workloads. *ACM SIGARCH Computer Architecture News* 44, 3 (2016), 153–165.
- [11] Zerui Guo, Jiabin Lin, Yuebin Bai, Daehyeok Kim, Michael Swift, Aditya Akella, and Ming Liu. 2023. LogNIC: A High-Level Performance Model for SmartNICs. In *Proceedings of the 56th Annual IEEE/ACM International Symposium on Microarchitecture*. 916–929.
- [12] Roman Heinrich, Manisha Luthra, Harald Kormmayer, and Carsten Binnig. 2022. Zero-shot cost models for distributed stream processing. In *Proceedings of the 16th ACM International Conference on Distributed and Event-Based Systems*. 85–90.
- [13] Mary Hogan, Shir Landau-Feibish, Mina Tahmasbi Arashloo, Jennifer Rexford, and David Walker. 2022. Modular switch programming under resource constraints. In *19th USENIX Symposium on Networked Systems Design and Implementation (NSDI 22)*. 193–207.
- [14] Shigeru Imai, Stacy Patterson, and Carlos A Varela. 2017. Maximum sustainable throughput prediction for data stream processing over public clouds. In *2017 17th IEEE/ACM International Symposium on Cluster, Cloud and Grid Computing (CCGRID)*. IEEE, 504–513.
- [15] Zsolt István, Gustavo Alonso, and Ankit Singla. 2018. Providing multi-tenant services with FPGAs: Case study on a key-value store. In *2018 28th International Conference on Field Programmable Logic and Applications (FPL)*. IEEE, 119–1195.
- [16] Zsolt István, David Sidler, and Gustavo Alonso. 2017. Caribou: Intelligent distributed storage. *Proceedings of the VLDB Endowment* 10, 11 (2017), 1202–1213.
- [17] Insoon Jo, Duck-Ho Bae, Andre S Yoon, Jeong-Uk Kang, Sangyeun Cho, Daniel DG Lee, and Jaeheon Jeong. 2016. YourSQL: a high-performance database system leveraging in-storage computing. *Proceedings of the VLDB Endowment* 9, 12 (2016), 924–935.
- [18] Frank P Kelly. 1976. Networks of queues. *Advances in Applied Probability* 8, 2 (1976), 416–432.
- [19] Patrick E O'Neil, Elizabeth J O'Neil, and Xuedong Chen. 2007. The star schema benchmark (SSB). *Pat* 200, 0 (2007), 50.
- [20] Martin Reiser and Stephen S Lavenberg. 1980. Mean-value analysis of closed multichain queuing networks. *Journal of the ACM (JACM)* 27, 2 (1980), 313–322.
- [21] Robert Schmid, Max Plauth, Lukas Wenzel, Felix Eberhardt, and Andreas Polze. 2020. Accessible near-storage computing with fpgas. In *Proceedings of the Fifteenth European Conference on Computer Systems*. 1–12.
- [22] Akshitha Sriraman and Abhishek Dhanotia. 2020. Accelerometer: Understanding acceleration opportunities for data center overheads at hyperscale. In *Proceedings of the Twenty-Fifth International Conference on Architectural Support for Programming Languages and Operating Systems*. 733–750.
- [23] Chunkai Wang, Xiaofeng Meng, Qi Guo, Zujian Weng, and Chen Yang. 2017. Automating characterization deployment in distributed data stream management systems. *IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering* 29, 12 (2017), 2669–2681.
- [24] Louis Woods, Zsolt István, and Gustavo Alonso. 2014. Ibox: An intelligent storage engine with support for advanced sql offloading. *Proceedings of the VLDB Endowment* 7, 11 (2014), 963–974.
- [25] Shuotao Xu, Thomas Bourgeat, Tianhao Huang, Hojun Kim, Sungjin Lee, and Arvind Arvind. 2020. Aquoman: An analytic-query offloading machine. In *2020 53rd Annual IEEE/ACM International Symposium on Microarchitecture (MICRO)*. IEEE, 386–399.
- [26] Zhe Yang, Youyou Lu, Xiaojian Liao, Youmin Chen, Junru Li, Siyu He, and Jiwei Shu. 2023. {λ-IO}: A Unified {IO} Stack for Computational Storage. In *21st USENIX Conference on File and Storage Technologies (FAST 23)*. 347–362.
- [27] Steffen Zeuch, Ankit Chaudhary, Bonaventura Monte, Haralampos Gavriilidis, Dimitrios Giouroukis, Philipp Grulich, Sebastian Breß, Jonas Traub, and Volker Markl. 2020. The NebulaStream Platform: Data and Application Management for the Internet of Things. In *Conference on Innovative Data Systems Research (CIDR)*.